

Biochemical estimation of Zn in blood/plasma

Manish Arya¹, Chaithra SN¹ and Pradeep Chandra²

¹Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, U.P., 243122

²Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Animal Reproduction, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, U.P., 243122

Introduction

Zinc, an essential trace element which helps in the various metabolic pathways, is required for growth and sexual development. It is a structure component of various proteins, help to regulate the activity of more than 300 enzymes and genetic expression control by synthesis and repair of DNA, RNA and protein. As a component of carbonic anhydrase, it helps in elimination of CO₂, alkaline phosphatase for phosphorylation, lactic dehydrogenase for interconversion of pyruvic and lactic acid. It is required for cell division, growth and differentiation, performance, development and aging in animals. Within visceral organs zinc is present in traces but skin, hair and wool contain zinc in high quantities. Zinc in serum is totally bound with protein with most of it (60%) bound to albumin.

Applications

Simple and direct procedures for measuring zinc concentration in biological samples for research and drug development. Zinc levels can be evaluated to help diagnose several disease processes

Increased zinc levels

- Gastro-intestinal disorders associated with nausea, vomition, high fever and metallic taste.

Decreased zinc levels

- Low dietary intakes
- Low bioavailability
- Malabsorption syndrome
- Chronic liver disease

- Chronic renal disease
- Sickle cell disease/anemia
- Diabetes
- Acute myocardial infarction (AMI)
- Malignancy (Lung carcinomas)
- Corticosteroids and other contraceptive therapy
- Other chronic illnesses.

Principle

- Serum Zinc is determined by Colorimetric method.
- The method utilizes a chromogen that forms a colored complex specifically with zinc.
- In alkaline medium, Zinc (Zn) reacts with **Nitro-PAPS** (2-(5 nitro-2-pyridylazo)-5-(Npropyl-N-sulfopropylamino) phenol disodium salt dehydrate) to form a purple colored complex. The intensity of color due to complex formed is directly proportional to the copper content present in the test sample.

Zinc + Nitro-PAPS --alkaline medium--→ Purple colored complex

Materials required

- Buffer reagent (L1)
- Color reagent (L2)
- Zinc standard of 200 microgram/dl (S)

The working reagent can be made by mixing 4 parts of L1 with 1 part of L2.

Sample collection and handling

- Serum sample used for estimation of zinc should be free from haemolysis.
- Samples for zinc estimation are stable for 7 days when stored at 2-8⁰C

Procedure

Label three clean dry test tubes as blank (B), standard (S) and test (T).

ADDITION SEQUENCE	BLANK (ml)	STANDARD (ml)	TEST (ml)
Working reagent	1.0	1.0	1.0
Distilled water	0.05	-	-
Zinc standard (S)	-	0.05	-

Sample	-	-	0.05
---------------	---	---	------

Mix the test tubes well and incubate for 10 minutes at room temperature (25⁰C)

Measure the absorbance of standard and test sample against the blank within 30 minutes.

Calculations or lab analysis

$$\text{Zinc in microgram/dl} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of test} \times 200}{\text{Zinc in microgram/dl}}$$

The procedure is linear upto 500 microgram/dl

Reference range in animals

The normal zinc level in animals is 20-120 mg/dl.

Interpretation

The color change is very small and is not visually evident.

The values remain interfered in physiological concentrations of other metal ions

The presence of chelating agents like EDTA/EGTA interfere with the development of colored complex, so should be avoided during sample preparation.

The samples should be cleared by centrifugation or filtration before use

Clinical significance

Deficiency of zinc may lead to following clinical anomalies:

- Reduced appetite and poor food utilization in zinc deficiency leads to poor growth in animals. They may appear stunted and dwarf.
- There is inappropriate growth of bones and the bones remain fragile due to decreased osteoblastic activity in zinc deficiency. Joints may become stiff and sometimes the lesions are well appreciated in the hoof areas.
- Zinc responsive dermatitis in which alopecia and generalized dermatitis may be seen around the head and neck region.
- Zinc deficiency and excess calcium may cause imperfect keratinization of the skin epithelial cells known as parakeratosis.
- Hyperkeratosis which is the excessive thickening of the skin may be seen in dairy cattle.
- Delayed sexual maturity, infertility and breeding obstacles, hypogonadism, fetal growth failure, teratology and abortion in the farm.
- Other clinical signs of zinc deficiency include acrodermatitis, low immunity, diarrhea, poor healing.

Diagnosis

- History of diet
- Clinical findings
- Estimation of zinc level
- Zinc deficiency may cause reduction in alkaline phosphatase and carbonic anhydrase level of serum.

References

Veterinary Medicine- A textbook of diseases of cattle, horses, sheep, pigs & goats (11th edition) by Peter D. Constable, Kenneth W Hinchcliff, Stanley H. Done and Walter Gruenberg.

<https://www.msdtvetmanual.com/special-subjects/reference-guides/serum-biochemical-reference-ranges>

Dukes' physiology of domestic animals (13th edition) by Willian O. Reece, Howard H. Erickson, Jesse P. Goff and Etsuro E. Uemura

https://www.abnova.com/protocol_pdf/KA1619.pdf

El-zebda, G.A., 2006. Significance of serum levels of copper and zinc in Type II diabetic, hypertensive, and diabetic hypertensive patients in Gaza City.